

[R' = Ph, Tol (*o*, *m* & *p*), naphthyl (α and β), *p*-chlorophenyl and *p*-phenetoyl]

The antitubercular activity of the amidines will be reported later on.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-2-Thiazolylamidines.—2-Aminothiazole (0.01 *M*), sodium (0.23 g.), and the nitrile (0.01 *M*) were refluxed in dry benzene (20 c.c.) in a 100 c.c. r.b. flask with a calcium chloride guard tube for 25 hours. Ethanol (5 c.c.) was added to dissolve any unchanged sodium as well as to decompose the sodio-amidine. The base after being converted into lactate was recovered by the addition of ammonia. The free amidines were recrystallised from acetone, ethanol or chloroform-petroleum ether.

TABLE I
N-2-Thiazolylamidines.

Amidine. (R=)	M.P.	% Yield.	Cryst. shape.	Cryst. from.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Calc.
<i>o</i> -Tol	205-207°	58	Dark brown powder	Acetone	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ S	18.90	19.35
<i>m</i> -Tol	133° (decomp.)	14	Brown powder	Chloroform-pet. ether	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ S	19.05	19.35
<i>p</i> -Tol	> 280°.	7	Do	Acetone	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ S	18.97	19.35
α -Naphthyl	177° (decomp.)	35	Do	Do	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ S	16.94	16.60
β -Naphthyl	160°	32	Do	Ethanol	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S	16.23	16.60
<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl	118-19°	88	Brown shining crystals	Do	C ₁₀ H ₆ N ₂ ClS	18.00	17.60
Phenetoyl	> 270°	17	Brown powder	Do	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S	16.72	17.00

6-Benzimidazolylammonium Benzenesulphonate (A).—To 6-nitrobenzimidazole (9 g.), dissolved in dry dioxane (70 c.c.) at 50-60° in a hydrogenating bottle, Adams' catalyst (10 mg.) was added and the mixture shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen at a pressure of 60 lbs. per sq. inch for 6 hours. The amine, so obtained in the solution being unstable, was immediately transferred to a 250 c.c. three-necked flask. Benzenesulphonic acid (1.5 g.), dissolved in dry methanol (5 c.c.), was added dropwise with stirring to this amine in solution. A white flocculent precipitate separated out; it was filtered, dried, and recrystallised from dioxane as a white amorphous powder, m.p. 232-33°, yield 98% (1.7 g.). (Found: N, 13.92. C₁₃H₁₃O₃N₃S requires N, 14.4%).

6-Benzimidazolylamidines.—The above compound (A) was converted into different 6-benzimidazolylamidine benzenesulphonates and the latter into the corresponding free amidines by the method adopted by us previously (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE II
6-Benzimidazolylamidine benzenesulphonates.

Compound. (R' =)	M.P.	% Yield.	Cryst. shape (Powder).	Crystallised from.
Ph	224-26°	46	Brown	Acetone
<i>o</i> -Tol	210°	57	"	"
<i>m</i> -Tol	207°	50	Dark brown	"
<i>p</i> -Tol	145° (decomp.)	57	Brown	"
α -Naphthyl	136° (decomp.)	66	Black	Ether
β -Naphthyl	164-65°	86	Brown	Acetone
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	201-202°	55	"	"
<i>p</i> -Phenetoyl	168-70°	13	"	Ethanol

TABLE III
6-Benzimidazolylamidines.

Amidines. (R' =)	M.P.	% Yield.	Cryst. shape (Powder)	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
Ph*	> 270°	13	Black	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄	23.35	23.70
<i>o</i> -Tol*	> 270°	30	"	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₄	22.80	22.40
<i>m</i> -Tol**	183-84°	12	"	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄	22.90	22.40
<i>p</i> -Tol*	> 275°	25	Dark brown	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₄	22.10	22.40
α -Naphthyl**	> 270°	26	Black	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄	19.17	19.58
β -Naphthyl*	202-203°	39	Grey	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄	19.10	19.58
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl**	> 270°	17	Dark brown	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₄ Cl	20.25	20.70
<i>p</i> -phenetoyl*	> 270°	39	Black	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ON ₄	19.70	20.00

* Crystallised from ethanol.

** " " " chloroform—pet. ether.

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